

Andrew C. Chapple

with: Ed Casanova, Naresh Pai, and
Zhenglei Gao

Bayer AG, Crop Science Division,
Monheim, DE

An aerial photograph of a large agricultural field. A tractor with a red and yellow sprayer is moving across the field, leaving a trail of dark, wet soil behind it. The field is divided into sections, some of which are green with crops, while others are brown and tilled. The sky is clear and blue.

*The Casanova Drift Model (CDM):
A mechanistic spray drift model for
ground application of plant
protection products*

Agenda

- // Why do we need a drift model?
- // The Casanova Drift Model
 - // General overview
 - // Calibration and validation in the US
 - // Considerations of
 - // Sampler collection efficiency
 - // Locale
 - // Drop spectra
 - // Calibration in the EU
- // Some conclusions...

Why do we need drift models?

- // To date, the Rautmann drift tables have been sufficient, but these are under scrutiny (and are rather old!)
- // Drift RA is a single Tier; higher tier approaches to an RA involving drift build on the drift tables (and there are no other options)
- // In a properly structured tiered RA, a regulatory model is one of the key components:
 - // C.f.: ground water, surface water. The tier involves various stages, either experimental (e.g., ecotox studies) to interpolations within data sets (e.g., birds and small mammals RUDs) to various modelling approaches (previous slide) to full scale field trials.
- // Arable crop drift values are in the process of being reassessed by EFSA – now ongoing – and are likely to be 3x to 15x higher than the current drift tables.
- // For non-target arthropods (NTAs) and non-target terrestrial plants (NTTPs), increased drift values are about a third of the overall increase in difficulty of regulatory acceptance. This brings the near-off-crop to prominence as an environmental compartment.
 - // Historically, water has been the principal environmental issue but the very limited mitigation options available for NTAs/NTTPs means that the near-off-crop will be of equivalent importance.

A Tiered RA for drift

A tiered RA for drift was the principal objective of SETAC DRAW. The Workshops and a lot subsequent work outside DRAW have delivered:

- 1. Data:** SETAC DRAW database (approx. 2200 drift trial) is now hosted at INRAE and is currently open to the researchers who supplied the data (8 EU countries plus Canada).
- 2. Statistical tools:** A Bayesian regression model based on the database can be used to explore scenarios as well as the confidence intervals around the drift curves generated.
- 3. Relevant scenarios:** The weakest link in the chain. Currently available data is very limited, mainly focused on N. Europe (esp. UK).
- 4. A model:** two models already exist (SiMod, UK; IDEFICS, NL). Neither are truly in the public domain, nor is the code available for outside development or scrutiny.
- 5. Up-to-date methodologies for drift trials:** the SETAC DRAW arable crop drift protocol is a template for future drift trials.
- 6. Laboratory methods:** Link actual spray drift to tiered testing (more on this at AAB IAPA, 2022, Sept. 2022 Munster, DE).
- 7. Trial designs:** NOED (no observable effect distance) trials – published and used by Syngenta and Bayer. These are the top tier assessments.

The Casanova Drift Model (CDM)

Developed in-house by Ed Casanova (ex-Monsanto, now in Bayer's Enabling Technology Team) as a tool for screening formulations to limit field trials.

Original programming in MathCad (so not user-friendly). Converted to 'R' and C++.

Principal components of model:

- // Droplet size distribution (DSD) – temporal data and at operating pressure to be modelled
- // Nozzle flow vs. pressure ([velocity of droplets](#) obtained here)
- // Tank solution density, total dissolved solids (DS) concentration, and check between intended application rate (IAR) for active, DS, NF, and Tractor speed (TS) (also important for [evaporation](#)).
- // Determination of wet bulb T depression (DTwb) for use in droplet [evaporation](#) equation
- // [Wind velocity profile](#) with elevation and horizontal variability in wind direction around mean relative to sprayed field – [turbulence](#) in direction of wind only. (Remaining two dimensions to be added.)
- // Deposition of droplets – converted to a [spray drift deposition curve](#).

The Casanova Drift Model (CDM)

SiMod, IDEFICS, and Casanova all follow the same physical descriptions. CDM is simpler than SiMod. [E.g., it does not include a droplet detrainment component nor any approach to crop canopies. (This is a level of sophistication that may come with time.)] CDM also differs from SiMod in taking a different approach to droplet sampling. Along with optimized routines, this makes it much faster.

CDM needs improvement / development on:

- // Turbulence description
- // Vertical distribution of droplets in flight
- // Expand nozzle description (more “slices”)
- // Flexibility in setting up the spray boom (currently a single 27 m boom is modelled)
- // Crop interception / filtration. (Currently limited to bare ground / short grass)

However, unlike the other arable crop drift models:

- // It is in the public domain already (hosted courtesy Jean-Paul Douzals at INRAE, Montpellier, FR).
- // It comes with a nozzle drop spectra library (all EU standard nozzles and pressures as found in the SETAC DRAW database)
- // All code (R and C++) will be freely available on request.

View of the model

[Just see me in any break and I will run it for you then...]

Droplet Size Distribution Results

DSD curve fitting performed? FALSE

Droplet Size Distribution Model Parameters

DSD curve fitting was not performed

Casanova Drift Model (CDM)

- User Guide
- Data Input
- Analysis
- Advanced

User Guide

This website provides an interactive tool to ...

Background

...

Drift Model

Subsection
Subsection

Data Description

...

Subsection

...

Transport Results

Deposition Results

Manually Input or Edit Parameters

Calibration and Validation: USA

Background from US work: Spray Drift Task Force data sets

The model has already been calibrated and validated against the US Spray Drift Task Force arable drift data set, but these data are very old and are for 80° flat fans (outdated) and has other issues. However, against modern field data, the results are also very good.

Calibration and Validation : USA

Bayer internal US field trials: nozzles and turbulence

Calibration and Validation: USA

Bayer internal US field trials: confirmation trial

Calibration and Validation: Europe

In general, all models have been developed in one country against a standardized set of local data: CDM is no exception.

However, there are significant differences between the data sets compiled by different country and research organisations (EU [8 sets], US, & Canada). One outcome from the collation and statistical analysis of the >2200 drift trials in the SETAC DRAW database is that 30-40% of the variance around drift measurements is driven by the country of origin.

This poses a problem...what is driving this variance that is unaccounted for by the existing variables measured in the trials? Some suggestions are (and in no particular order):

1. Differences in sampler efficiency.
2. Large scale upwind effects (buildings, the sea, rolling hills, *etc.*, *etc.*).
3. Drop spectra used as input.

1. Sampler collection efficiency

Different research institutes have used different deposition samplers.

BE: square creped filter paper, mounted on steel plates

UK: filter paper mounted on laths

DE: petri dishes

NL: filter pads in either squares or strips

US: Bayer - petri dishes; SDTF - mylar plates

Statistical analysis of the trials gave us more questions than answers...trial data was too variable to be useful to find conversion factors.

Wind tunnel work confirmed differences, but they are not large...

Silsoe Spray Applications Unit Ltd

Higher wind speed

1. Sampler collection efficiency

Differences are dynamic: the samplers behave differently with downwind distance and within sampler type.

Capture efficiency of a simple petri dish varies with wind speed (see right) and is unlikely to be consistent across small to large droplet spectra [but recent work suggests something different for capture...]

CDM: we are building in a sampler efficiency module (for experts!) to attempt to take this into account.

Examples of sampler positioning and mounting

In the SETAC DRAW database, these are all “sampler type = petri dishes”

2. Locale

France

The Netherlands

2. Locale

Poland

3. Drop Spectra

Which measurement system to use?

Drop spectra are measured in different ways and typically models have been developed based on the drop spectra measurement system available to the modellers. For example:

- // IDEFICS and the BE CFD model: phase-doppler particle sizing (PDPA, e.g., Aerometrics)
- // SiMod: PDPA and now high-speed laser imaging (Oxford Lasers) but also laser diffraction.
- // CDM: laser diffraction (Malvern) in a constant wind speed (US drop sizing protocol).

These all differ in output and have different issues and advantages, e.g.:

- PDPA cannot handle formulations reliably;
- Laser diffraction interpolates from a cloud of drops;
- Speed of data acquisition varies a lot.

All methods require expertise in setting up which leads to some subjectivity in the measurements. Thus, different modelled drift deposition curves can be obtained from the same nozzle at the same operating pressure. (Let's not look at formulations...)

For the future, we need some means of translating between drop size measurements – a stock library drawn from all methods?

Calibration and Validation: General

[To be published at AAB International Advances in Spray Application, Munster, Sept. 2022]

Any arable drift model has to be calibrated against three expectations (in order!):

1. Output needs to make sense (*e.g.*, smaller drop spectra generate more drift). (No physical laws are to be broken.)
2. The relative differences obtained in changing variables (*e.g.*, windspeed) need to match the differences seen in the field.
3. Can the model can be tuned to properly match trial outcomes (within limits).

...and, of course, sensitivity analysis and “edge of envelope” testing.

Calibration and Validation: General

Does the CDM output make sense?

Baseline scenario is average for all French spray drift trials using:

48 x AIX 11002 nozzle spraying 105 L/ha water at 250 kPa at 0.65 m spacing 0.5 m above 0.15 m high 'crop';

18.6°C at 68%RH in a wind speed of 3.35 m/s (WBD 3.66) under neutral conditions

Conditions varied :

Droplet evaporation by varying %RH (*i.e.*, wet bulb depression)

Boom height

Wind speed

Outputs: evaporation

Higher WBD leads to smaller droplets which leads to less drift with distance. Large droplets close to the edge-of-field are much less affected due to their larger size.

(The small change in reducing WBD needs to be investigated...)

Outputs: boom height

Higher booms lead to higher drift

Outputs: wind speed

Higher windspeed means more drift but effects beyond 10-12 m are quite variable. (We know that this is a function of simplified detrainment model used: for a flat fan is only three 'slices': ten works a lot better but adds a lot of computational time).

Relative differences: paired trials

Boom height

Model clearly over-shoots the field data by a large margin. However, the data suggests only a small effect of boom height: the model is more in keeping with other published data. Trial may be seeing interception by the turf...?

AXI 11002 at 250 kPa, 24 m boom at 0.5 and **0.7 m above 0.15 m** high turf.

WBD 3.8° & 3.8°

Wind speed 2.44 & 2.44 m/s

° from perpendicular 11.3° & -1.4°

Relative differences: paired trials

Wet Bulb Depression

Model clearly under-shoots the field data, but the data suggests a decrease in drift with increased evaporation. The model is at least intuitively correct, even at distance.

FF 11003 at 300 kPa, 27 m boom at 0.5 above bare ground.

WBD **1.8° & 4.8°**

Wind speed 2.08 & 2.09 m/s

° from perpendicular 1.24° & 20°

Relative differences: paired trials

Wind speed

Model tracks the field data, but the deposition lines cross, which is counter-intuitive and runs contrary to the data and general experience. The output indicates that a better detrainment analysis is needed.

XR 11004 at 300 kPa, 24 m boom at 0.5 above bare ground.

WBD 3.2° & 3.2°

Wind speed **3.5 & 1.8 m/s**

° from perpendicular 2.7° & 1.4°

Relative differences: paired trials

Wind speed and wet bulb depression

Model indicates that wind speed is driving drift rather than WBD, relative to the data...needs thought.

FF 11003 at 300 kPa, 27 m boom at 0.5 above grassland.

WBD **8.9° & 1.0°**

Wind speed **2.5 & 0.96 m/s**

° from perpendicular 1.24° & 20°

Relative differences: paired trials

Drop spectra (pressure a surrogate for drop size)

Model tracks the trial data but without the crossover at ca. 10 m.

FF 11003 at **200 kPa / 400 kPa**, 27 m boom at 0.5 above 0.1 m high grass.

WBD **1.3° & 3.9°**

Wind speed 2.75 / 2.73 m-s

° from perpendicular 25.2° & 37.6°

Conclusions so far...

Some insights from SETAC DRAW and CDM development so far.

// Any model has to be:

// useable in any regulatory domain (EU, USA, LATAM) or country.

// deal with differences in upwind structures that affect the overall wind profile.

// tuneable to a given country's drift trials and data.

// agnostic with respect to inputs such as drop spectra and variability from sources such as sampler capture efficiency.

// able to generate deposition curves and short range aerial drift (linking to off-crop capture, HuSa)

// The CDM needs:

// greater sophistication in the drop detrainment description and turbulence description

// a broader based drop spectra library.

// handle crops (even primitively).

// Much fundamental research is needed in order to ensure matching of models to data.

*Thank you for
your attention...*

